

Business Intelligence Tools and Team Performance of Oil and Gas Industries

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Abstract--- Business intelligence have been flourishing as a result of its increasing role in business performance, data integration and warehousing, forecasting, financial plan, and the decision-making process, which directs business operations toward positive performance. These days business intelligence has become a developing trend in managing the decision-making for directing the changing atmosphere, and also intending to take opportunities evolving form changing conditions. Business intelligence (BI) in any organization is referred to as “the method of incorporation of information from various internal and external sources, using analysis tools to empathize the information within the records, decision- making, on the basis of this gained insight. At the same time teamwork is believed to be a tool that intends to improve manpower exploitation and positively increasing performance of not only the individual employee but the whole organization eventually, since it could increase the productivity of individuals through group effort. This research is an attempt to identify the role that the usage of Business Intelligence tools play in enhancing the team performance of the staff working with respect to the oil and gas based organizations in the Middle East. This research adapts a quantitative approach. Data has been collected from 312 employees working at either top or middle level management of the most reputed Oil and Gas Companies in the Middle East. The results reveal that Business Intelligence tools do create an impact in enhancing the overall team performance of the employees working at the organization.

Keywords--- Business Intelligence Tools, Oil and Gas Industry, Team Performance, Employees.

I. Introduction

With increasing number of information given by the development of technology, BI is seen as main attribute for thriving management of the related data for business to give support for the processes of the decision making (Dhandayudam and Krishnamurthi, 2013). According to Balan and Rege (2017) BI includes all systems and processes for example data marts, warehouses for data, analytical tools like in-memory analytics, data mining, OLAP (Online Analytical Process) and ad hoc analytics, forecasts, planning, data mining and scorecards which changes raw information into practical and important data which will be systematic, focused and useful interpretation in the company and its competitive business area (Zekic-Susac, 2015). It is significant for organizations to identify and develop related and vital data among huge amount of information produced in industry every day. If BI is utilized for enhancing decision making processes (Gaardboe et al, 2007) or for improving processes of business (Vera-Baquero et al, 2015), it would influence the performance of the organization. Thus if BI is used and applied, it will be added advantage for the organization. On the other hand most of the organizations do not reach the proper advantages from adopting BI (Schick et al, 2011 and Isik et al, 2011). Further it was added by Clavier et al (2012) that about 60 to 70 percent of applications of BI fail because of infrastructure, organizational, cultural and technology. Azeroual and Theel (2018) elucidated that with growing markets globalization, maximizing speed with modifications of business area and consumer requirements, heavy competition and companies are able to declare themselves, adjust to such conditions, and respond openly and rapidly to modifications and having their expenses under control. Nevertheless, correct knowledge of present market and business situation is crucial. For ensuring this and for providing management with data required in their decision making and planning, stylish communication and information systems are adopted. From 1960s, difference approaches were adopted for such systems which are recognized under various names like decision support systems, management information system and executive information systems. At present, the term BI was well-known in research as well as in practice. It stores, analyze, collect, present and process business information.

People working in oil and gas firm will collect, store, analyze, consume or interpret few data forms. This industry not only concentrates on adopting data for gaining operational competence and focus on enhancing the organizational performance. These companies adopt data for analyzing main assets and exacting value. However, BI appears to be one of types into field itself. In oil and gas industry geoscientists, engineers and all other workers were taught business intelligence from beginning. Everybody in the field have the same opinion about significance of good BI and its improved performance. BI is not only about getting a set of tools for analyzing and feeding

information into them. At the same time, when it is adopted and implemented properly it will be added competitive advantage to the field (Entrance, 2012).

Table 1: BI Tools Adopted in Business

Tools	Domains of applications	Strengths	Weaknesses
Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL) and data cleaning	Huge data bases, disseminated, internet and heterogeneous data	Transformation, extraction and more data is passed automatically	Require software with high quality to ETL, IT professionals and specialists
Text mining	Electronic mail, corporate documents, communication, web	To process and analyze unstructured contents of web	Difficultly in adopting techniques of text mining and few complex in analysis of acquired outcomes
OLTP (Online Analytical Processing)	Warehouses for data, virtual marts for data	Shorter the time data horizon inside the OLTP when compared with OLAP	Require strong servers for databases, processors with high quality and SQL servers
Tools for interactive visualization and dashboards	Data visualization, dynamic visualization for business, user interface for real-time, interactive optimization and simulations	Using various methodologies, giving high analytics and graphs for interactive business, sixsigma, contributed to managers	Current status presentation, organizational trends, required high quality software (ActiveX, Adobe and Java) and hardware
Predictive modelling and activities for data mining	Analysis and forecast	Large databases analysis, finding out new patterns and correlations	Require knowledge on various mathematical models and methods, contributed to small users group
Web mining	Social media, cloud computing and opinion mining	Integrate different content from various systems which is web enabled, economic value added.	Difficult adoption of techniques for web mining and some complex in analysis and acquired outcomes
OLAP	Data warehouses and marts	sum up the views of data used for business, multi-dimensional, conducted difficult analyses	Difficult building process, adopting data warehouses and giving data about operations of business with lengthy latency
Search based application	Identify data in any format and any type of source	Not dependent from IT departments, perform with previous systems for information	Difficult development process of such application
In-memory databases and real-time BI	Mobile devices, big data, social media, resources from internet and blogs	On-demand process, in real-time	Require high ended software as well as hardware
ERGM (Exponential random graph models)	Large-scale visualization and analysis of network, different social networks, web services.	Adoption of mobile platforms namely IOS and Android	Needed statistical models knowledge
NoSQL	Social media, big data, blogs, resources from internet and mobile devices	Practising and analyzing of data which is semi-structured	Require high quality software and hardware, complicated statistical methods for data processing and analyzing

Source: Olszak and Zurada (2015)

Table 1 deploys various BI tools adopted in business organizations.

Figure 1: Revenue of BI Tools

Source: Zion Market Research (n,d) as Cited in Finances Online (2019)

Figure 1 illustrates revenue of BI software. Many business firms adopt BI tools for growth; promotion for BI tools is expected to grow further. Global market for BI tool is predicted to develop at a CAGR of about 7.1 percent through 2025. As depicted in table 2, the market is expected to strike above the \$26-B mark in the year 2021. Expansion of market is anticipated as the technology will pave way in assisting industry to grow.

Figure 2: Business Value and Impact of BI Tools

Source: Report, n,d

Figure 2 depicts business value and impact of BI tools. Each tool have different functionality like prediction for advanced analytics, analysis for OLAP and data visualization, monitoring for dashboards score cards and reporting for query and reporting.

II. Theoretical Development and Hypothesis

Figure 3: The Conceptual Framework for the Business Intelligence tools and Team Performance

Source: Author

Figure 3 depicts the conceptual framework for the business intelligence tools and team performance.

Venuturumilli et al (2016) identified that there is significant relationship between data quality and endogenous factors in BI identified that advanced technological tools are altering data into useful information for quality and taking better decisions that will help added advantage for the workers and improve the performance of the organization. However Jamaludin and Mansor (2011) mentioned that having commitment in top management will assist to eliminate more issues to greater adoption of BI like issues in human capital, lack of money, time, skilled resources and labor. Involvement of end-user, expert project team and resources availability are main part for adopting a successful BI project.

It was found out by Keikha (2016) that strategic intelligence components that is competitive intelligence, management of knowledge and BI) can assist managers for enhancing the employees performance. In addition to that, Foster et al (2015) stated that for evaluating the BI project success by these criteria namely margin generated (profitability of consumers and performance), maximize customers, high sales, standardization and optimization of data, people performance which perform with information acquired from the projects. Successes are assessed at various levels such as output of the report, support and collaboration with other field. Every person participated in the project are indirectly or directly included in estimation. There is positive effect at organizational and individual levels in the success of BI implementation. Saavedra and Bach (2017) proved that satisfaction of user, reducing the cost and optimization of time shapes the process of decision making with the help of BI applications.

H1.0: There is no relationship between the Usage of business intelligence tools create an impact in enhancing the overall team performance of the employees working at the Oil and Gas based organizations in the Middle East

Olsak (2014), Abai et al (2019), Conn (2015) and Olsak (2014b) stated that BI is important for most of the organizational success. BI allows them to acquire speed and easier right to get information, to enhance processes of business and decision making and for identifying the treats and chances whereas cooperate with competitors, suppliers and customers. Further Kao et al (2016) and Mate et al (2016) added that BI provides information about the business, market, environment and institutional market trends.

Al-Zubi et al (2014) pointed out that key part of managing the accounting is to adopt a present data in the best potential method for making the high quality decisions. To handle information and maximize the information system efficiency are accomplished by implementation of BI tools. Adoption of BI tools has positive and significant impact on information management, process of decision making thus save money and time. Further, Khan et al (2012) and

Pejic-Bach et al (2018) argued that applications of BI assisted the companies to overcome many issues namely overload of information whereas there is requirement for extracting a expensive data from the information. Without having proper information and idea, it takes more time for management and workers for planning future steps and way for running the operation easily; consequently result in poor performance in time delivery, higher cost production, poor planning of production and so on (Yusof et al, 2014).

Personal and technological capabilities are two mechanisms in the capability of information management, insights of the firms encompass the characteristic of personnel capability and resources of firm include technological capability. Thus management of information is considered as valid dependent value of capability in the organization. Skill oriented support and organizational material is given for appropriate information management (Brinkhues et al, 2014) as well as allocation needs support for implementing BI in business. Managing the information is main need for the decision making and BI is considered as best performer of management of information (Ali et al, 2017, Isik et al, 2013, Chen et al, 2012, Thamir et al, 2015 and Citroen, 2011). Thus needed capability appropriate to management of information is significant in adopting BI (Brinkhues et al, 2014 and Mithas et al, 2011). In addition to that, Rodionov and Tsvetkova (2015) claimed that components of managing the information are technology of information management, administration for information and organizational information.

H2.0: There is no relationship between the Usage of business intelligence tool aids in information management in Oil and Gas Sector based organizations in the Middle East

Chen et al (2012) highlighted that with the help of decision making and sensing tasks, companies learn from new actions and generate new knowledge, rules and data that systems of business intelligence store and directs across various commerce departments and units share through technologies for communication that could support tasks in collaborative action. Communication technologies and BI technologies are appropriate fit to tasks for managing the event in the process of sense-response by properly giving such actions that appropriately sustain all the responsibilities. However, Leelavathy et al (2016) stated that BI eases detection and analysis of information and make it feasible for decision-makers at all organizational levels to easily analyze, understand access, act on data and collaborate, anywhere and anytime.

Olszak and Batko (2012) argued that decision making is naturally a collaborative job and integrating social software with BI (collaborative BI) can gradually maximize the decision making quality. Conversely present solutions for BI will give basic capabilities for collaboration. Decision making in the collaborative way is performed system outside with the help of other tools or channels for communication like conversations in phone or emails. Such expensive, lengthy and bulk processes delay businesses and have negative effect on implementing analytical tool.

BI tools constantly check huge amounts of information produced by the firm and cautiously examine it for few metrics for performance like marketing costs, sales figures and efficiency in real time. This assists maintain top management discussed about performance and significance of different vital components inside the business and collaboration between units of business. It allows business administrative for identifying business chances and make benefit of them (Analytics, n,d). Output of BI focuses on creator or solution of better decision as well as acts as a device that allows reflection, collaboration and dialogue among BI decision-makers and managers. Additionally, managers computed the impact of BI on reflection, dialogue and collaboration and outcomes of decision (Shollo, 2013).

H3.0: There is no relationship between the Usage of business intelligence tool aids in collaboration among employees working at Oil and Gas Sector based organizations in the Middle East

Al-ma'aitah (2013) found that there is significant impact of adopting BI tools in process of decision making. BI system and such tools have a close link with process of decision making. It support decision for minimizing the time and remove human errors and cost. If the system of BI achieves their needs then decision making processes will be direct, effective and remove wastage of time and threat will be minimized and confusion is not seen in the performance. Nawaz (2015) identified that from the stakeholders' point of view, advancement of technology, strategic planning, management of knowledge and organizational support has important effect on success of IT systems for supporting decision making.

Azeroual and Theel (2018) elucidated that BI is an appropriate tool for start-ups and successful management. Systems of BI change the huge volume of data of individual effective systems into practical information. Further, it was stated that BI tools for examining and evaluating the main database carry each day executive's work and give the fundamental for strategic decisions. Many investigators Thamir et al (2015), Obeidat (2015) and Olexova, 2014 have pointed out that BI tools enhance decision-making in terms of optimization for stock, enhanced ability, excellence decision making for expecting earlier modifies are seen in the market as mentioned by lstrat et al, 2015.

H4.0: There is no relationship between the Usage of business intelligence tool aids in better decision making with respect to Oil and Gas Sector based organizations in the Middle East

III. Research Methodology

The methodology of research followed is quantitative paradigm. Moreover, descriptive design was adopted as the research design of the study. By adopting quantitative methodology, hypothesis testing is performed with statistical data. Questionnaire was developed for studying usage of BI tools like information management, collaboration and decision making as well as studying the team performance of BI. This research also studies benefits of BI tools rendered in the organization and also studied about challenges faced by BI in the organization. Target inhabitants of this research is employees working at either middle or top level management of most reputed oil and gas companies in the Middle East. Target size of this particular research is 312 employees. This specific research makes use of probability sampling and randomly respondents were selected. This research adopts simple random sampling. This research adopts both primary and secondary data. Primary data was gathered from 312 employees working at either middle or top level management of one of most reputed oil and gas companies in the Middle East. Statistical tools adopted in this research are SPSS, MLR, r square value, anova significance and r value.

Reliability is considered as the overall construct consistency and its items. Here in this research out of 6 items 4 constructs are found to be above 0.9 which indicates our constructs are highly reliable. Reliability statistics and total statistics of information management are illustrated in Table 2 and Table 3. Alpha values for the information management are illustrated in Table 3

Table 2: Reliability Statistics for Information Management

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
BITIM1	14.7346	15.378	.622	.904
BITIM2	14.6142	13.872	.820	.876
BITIM3	14.7500	14.522	.713	.892
BITIM4	14.4074	14.298	.725	.890
BITIM5	14.4630	13.940	.758	.885
BITIM6	14.4383	13.758	.794	.880

Table 3: Item-Total Statistics for information management

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.940	6

Table 4: Reliability Statistics for Decision Making

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.905	6

Table 5: Item-Total Statistics for Decision Making

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
BITBDM1	20.1111	9.864	.795	.932
BITBDM2	20.1543	9.697	.838	.927
BITBDM3	20.1543	9.648	.858	.924
BITBDM4	20.1636	9.648	.868	.923
BITBDM5	20.0988	9.842	.821	.929
BITBDM6	20.0741	10.069	.740	.938

Reliability statistics for decision making and item-total statistics for decision making are depicted in Table 4 and Table 5. Alpha values for decision making are shown in Table 5.

Table 6: Reliability Statistics for Collaboration

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.813	4

Table 7: Item-Total Statistics for Collaboration

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
BITC1	8.5401	6.070	.632	.766
BITC2	7.9660	6.113	.654	.756
BITC3	8.6605	6.021	.626	.769
BITC4	8.5093	5.966	.618	.773

Reliability statistics for collaboration and item-total statistics for collaboration are depicted in Table 6 and Table 7. Alpha values for collaboration are shown in Table 7

Table 8: Reliability Statistics for Team Performance

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.941	7

Table 9: Item-Total Statistics for Team Performance

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
TP1	24.2037	13.420	.810	.932
TP2	24.2407	13.310	.828	.930
TP3	24.2346	13.388	.829	.930
TP4	24.2469	13.252	.873	.926
TP5	24.1821	13.499	.822	.931
TP6	24.1667	13.607	.767	.936
TP7	24.1327	14.128	.715	.940

Reliability statistics for team performance and item-total statistics for team performance are depicted in Table 8 and Table 9. Alpha values for team performance are shown in Table 9

Table 10: Reliability Statistics for Benefits of BI

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.921	14

Table 11: Item-Total Statistics for Benefits of BI

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
BBIT1	48.1728	57.580	.635	.916
BBIT2	48.1543	56.744	.698	.913
BBIT3	48.1111	56.495	.733	.912
BBIT4	47.9136	57.745	.720	.913
BBIT5	48.2531	57.100	.655	.915
BBIT6	47.9846	57.854	.691	.914
BBIT7	47.9259	57.487	.703	.913
BBIT8	47.8920	59.793	.585	.917
BBIT9	47.7747	59.841	.605	.917
BBIT10	47.7778	59.560	.610	.917
BBIT11	47.9043	59.647	.587	.917
BBIT12	47.9074	59.409	.649	.915
BBIT13	47.7191	59.800	.560	.918
BBIT14	47.8148	59.829	.608	.917

Reliability statistics for benefits of BI and item-total statistics for benefits of BI are depicted in Table 10 and Table 11. Alpha values for benefits of BI are shown in Table 11

Table 12: Reliability Statistics for Challenges faced by BI

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.894	8

Table 13: Item-Total Statistics for Challenges Faced by BI

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
C1	27.0433	15.495	.658	.882
C2	27.1734	15.392	.647	.883
C3	26.9350	15.701	.657	.882
C4	27.1269	14.794	.725	.875
C5	27.3282	14.948	.595	.889
C6	27.2786	14.518	.727	.875
C7	27.1827	14.659	.697	.878
C8	27.1703	14.695	.692	.878

Reliability statistics for challenges faced by BI and item-total statistics for Challenges faced by BI are depicted in Table 12 and Table 13. Alpha values for challenges faced by BI are shown in Table 13.

Table 14: Alpha Value of all Constructs

S.NO	Construct	ITEMS	ALPHA
1	Information management	6	.905
2	Better decision making	6	.940
3	Collaboration	4	.813
4	Team performance	7	.941
5	Benefits that business intelligence tools	14	.921
6	Challenges faced	8	.894

Table 14 depicts alpha value of all constructs. Alpha value for information management is 0.905 which is highly reliable. Alpha value for better decision making is 0.940 which is highly reliable. Alpha value for collaboration is 0.813 which is reliable. Alpha value for team performance is 0.941 which is highly reliable. Alpha value for benefits of adopting BI tools is 0.921 which is highly reliable. Alpha value for challenges faced by BI is 0.894 which is reliable.

This research carried out validity test for verifying whether the instrument selected for this research exactly gives the outcomes what is premeditated to be calculated.

IV. Model Fitness

Here research model fit is verified the r square value, r value and anova significance were all tested using multiple linear regression (MLR). Outcomes of the MLR are tabulated below.

Table 15: Regression Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
TPMEAN	4.0343	.61036	324
MEANIMP	2.9136	.74862	324
MEANDM	4.0234	.62000	324
MEANC	2.8279	.79670	324
MEANB	3.6892	.58572	324

Regression descriptive statistics are shown in Table 15. Standard deviation and the mean for the sample is identified and tabulated above.

Table 16: Correlations between Constructs

Correlations						
		TPMEAN	MEANIMP	MEANDM	MEANC	MEANB
Pearson Correlation	TPMEAN	1.000	.310	.991	.278	.630
	MEANIMP	.310	1.000	.303	.388	.459
	MEANDM	.991	.303	1.000	.275	.617
	MEANC	.278	.388	.275	1.000	.334
	MEANB	.630	.459	.617	.334	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	TPMEAN	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
	MEANIMP	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
	MEANDM	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
	MEANC	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
	MEANB	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
N	TPMEAN	324	324	324	324	324
	MEANIMP	324	324	324	324	324
	MEANDM	324	324	324	324	324
	MEANC	324	324	324	324	324
	MEANB	324	324	324	324	324

The correlation table between constructs in the MLR reports evidently discloses the correlation between the constructs. Table 17 illustrates variables entered or removed. Dependent variable is TPMEAN. All requested variables in this research are entered.

Table 17: Variables Entered/Removed

Variables Entered/Removed ^a			
Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	MEANB, MEANC, MEANIMP, MEANDM ^b	.	Enter
a. Dependent Variable: TPMEAN			
b. All requested variables entered.			

Table 18: The r Table

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.991 ^a	.982	.982	.08267	.982	4321.884	4	319	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), MEANB, MEANC, MEANIMP, MEANDM									
b. Dependent Variable: TPMEAN									

The r table shows the coefficient of multiple correlation and R value. R is seen as the one measure for the prediction quality of the dependent variable. R value about 0.991 shows the good prediction level, the value of r square was known as coefficient of willpower that is variance proportion in the dependent variable which can be described by the independent variables. Constant predictors are MEANB, MEANIMP, MEANC and MEANDM. Dependent variable is TPMEAN.

Table 19: Anova Table

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	118.150	4	29.537	4321.884	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.180	319	.007		
	Total	120.330	323			
a. Dependent Variable: TPMEAN						
b. Predictors: (Constant), MEANB, MEANC, MEANIMP, MEANDM						

The Anova table also known as statistical significance table provides the ratio of F and tests whether the overall model of regression is a good and best fit for the data. Anova table illustrates the independent variables significantly and statistically identify the dependent variable. F(4319) =29.537, $p < .0005$ that is model of regression is a good fit of data.

Table 20: Coefficient Table

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.067	.034		1.996	.047
	MEANIMP	.001	.007	.001	.128	.898
	MEANDM	.957	.009	.972	101.044	.000
	MEANC	.001	.006	.001	.092	.926
	MEANB	.031	.011	.029	2.848	.005

a. Dependent Variable: TPMEAN

The coefficients of estimated model takes the general equation form for predicting the enhanced team performance from management of information, decision making, collaboration and tools of business intelligence is acquired from the coefficient table is explained in table 20.

Table 21: Residuals Statistics

Residuals Statistics ^a					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	1.2988	5.0113	4.0343	.60480	324
Residual	-.76874	.30120	.00000	.08216	324
Std. Predicted Value	-4.523	1.615	.000	1.000	324
Std. Residual	-9.299	3.643	.000	.994	324

a. Dependent Variable: TPMEAN

Table 21 represents residuals statistics.

Figure 4: Regression Standardized Residual

Fig. 4 represents regression standardized residual. Mean and standard deviation is shown in chart 4

Figure 5: Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Figure 5 represents normal P-P Plot of regression standardized residual. Expected cum prob and observed cum prob are shown in the chart.

V. Analysis and Discussion

Accepted hypothesis from the outcomes of the testing are as follows. It was clear there is a relationship between the usage of business intelligence tools create an impact in enhancing the overall team performance of the employees working at the Oil and Gas based organizations in the Middle East. There is a relationship between the Usage of business intelligence tool aids in information management in Oil and Gas Sector based organizations in the Middle East. There is a relationship between the Usage of business intelligence tool aids in collaboration among employees working at Oil and Gas Sector based organizations in the Middle East. There is a relationship between the Usage of business intelligence toolaids in better decision making with respect to Oil and Gas Sector based organizations in the Middle East.

Usage of BI tools aids in information management. It helps in reducing the effort in analyzing and reporting the data. It assists in accessing the information easily. It was also found out that information can be acquired rapidly with better quality. BI improves the support in data. It enhances the efficiency in the operations. It gives more prefect planning, analysis or reporting. Usage of BI tools aids in taking better decision making. It enhances the process of decision making. Opportunities and threats are supported thus outcomes are enhanced. More sensible analysis for the data process assists to ease the process of decision making in the business. It gives ease of understanding and effectiveness of decisions. Further, it was noted that it gives better business strategies, decisions and tactics. It gives support for the attempt of planned objectives of business. Usage of BI tools aids in collaboration. It was clear from the analysis that teams are generally collaborative. It assists teams to coordinate themselves and share chances towards the common objective. It develop relationships between inter and organization. It effectively manages process of inter-organizational and securely share the information given by management. Thus it is clear from the analysis that usage of BI tools aids in information management, collaboration and better decision making.

By implementing the BI tools in the organization team performance are enhanced. Goals in the organization are achieved by team members. Predicted scope of the job is finished on time by team members. The predicted quality

of task is accomplished by the team members on time. Work operations are performed effectively by team members. Schedule is strictly followed by the team members. Work operations are performed by the members in the team without any delays. Members in the team maintain more confidence in the working place and at the time of project operation. Thus it is clear from the analysis that BI tools do create an impact in improving the team performance of the employees working at the organization.

It assists the organization in giving timely solutions to the business questions. It assists organization for enhancing policies with better analysis of marketing. It assists to remove report backlog and delays. It helps the working place to acquire better contracts with supplies and customers. It helps the organization to identify the wasted resources as well as aids in minimizing the inventory costs. It enhances satisfaction of the employee, minimizes time and effort put manually, maximizes the organizational revenue and enhances the consumer satisfaction. It will be added advantage for the organization. In addition to that, it was found out that it saves time and cost from consolidation of data. It gives capacity to company to handle huge amount of information. It gives flexibility and easiness in accessing information. It assists the organization to provide reporting design in real time. As explained by Saavedra and Bach (2017) that reducing the cost, satisfaction of user and optimization of time shapes the process of decision making with the help of BI applications.

Even though there are many benefits associated with implementing BI tools in the organizations it is not free from its restrictions. Challenges faced by implementing BI tools are namely lack of resources in team while completing the project, top management lacks support, lack of communication among team members, lack of tight deadline and training, team faces issues related to software, software is inflexible to adopt, security issues and migration of data is main issue.

VI. Conclusion and Future Work

Business intelligence helps to boost performance in the organization. It is evident from the analysis that the data is considered as significant and precious part to the organization as well as considered as essential for success and performance in the organization. It was noted that BI helps firms to understand better, to make quality decision for business as well as aids in adjusting to unpredictable atmosphere in order to sustain in the competitive world. This investigation is an effort to find out the role that the usage of BI tools play in improving the performance of team of the staff working with specific reference to oil and gas based organizations in the Middle East. It can be concluded from the findings of the research are as follows: There is a relationship between the usage of business intelligence tools creates an impact in enhancing the overall team performance. There is a relationship between the usage of business intelligence tool aids in information management. There is a relationship between the usage of business intelligence tool aids in collaboration. There is a relationship between the usage of business intelligence tool aids in better decision making.

It can be concluded that more sensible analysis for the data process assists to ease the process of decision making in the business. In addition to that, it helps to understand better and make quality decisions. BI tools assist teams to coordinate themselves and share chances towards the common objective and at the same time it develop relationships between inter and organization. Further, it was evident from the study that information can be acquired rapidly with better quality with the help of BI tools. BI improves the support in data as well as enhances the efficiency in the operations. When implementing BI in the organization it enhances satisfaction of the employee, maximizes the organizational revenue, minimizes time and effort put manually and enhances the consumer satisfaction. Further, it was clear that BI will be added advantage for the organization.

This research will be eye opener for the investigators and researchers to understand the importance of implementing BI tools and its performance in the oil and gas based organizations. This investigation is also not free from margins. Inhabitants selected for this study are employees working at either middle or top level management. Target size of the research is 312 participants. This research is restricted to business intelligence tools adopted in the oil and gas companies in the Middle East. Findings of the research cannot be used generally and adopted for the oil and gas companies only. This investigation further prolonged by finding out the verified hypothesis of data collected from miscellaneous group of inhabitants from others sectors like automobile companies, business sectors, healthcare, education field and so on in the future.

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